

IMPLEMENTING OF THE OPTIMIZED TRUCK SEAT PLATE MADE OF THERMOPLASTIC GF/PP COMPOSITE

Edgars Labans¹, Kaspars Kalnins¹, Eduards Skukis¹ and Philippe Lefort², Clement Dufour³,
Wolfgang Trümper⁴, Tim Callin⁴

¹ Institute of Materials and Structures, Riga Technical University
Azenes iela 16/20, LV-1048, Riga, Latvia
Email: edgars.labans@rtu.lv, kaspars.kalnins@rtu.lv, edskukis@gmail.com
web page: <http://www.ims.rtu.lv/en/>

²Volvo Group Trucks Technology, 69802 Saint Priest, France
69802 Saint Priest, France
Email: philippe.lefort@volvo.com, web page: www.volvogroup.com

³GEMTEX
59056 Roubaix Cedex1, France
Email: clement.dufour@ensait.fr, web page: <http://www.gemtex.fr/>

⁴Institute of Textile Machinery and High Performance Material Technology (ITM), TU Dresden
01062 Dresden, Germany
Email: Tim.Callin@tu-dresden.de, Wolfgang.Truemper@tu-dresden.de
web page: <https://tu-dresden.de>

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ABSTRACT

In current research design, optimisation and prototyping of truck cabin seat plate made of thermoplastic GF/PP composite has been performed. In particular study a conventional steel sheet material has been substituted by lightweight thermoplastic alternative. Such a design should enable a possibility of quick one shot manufacturing of composite structure and in addition it provides a significant weight savings. As a basis for redesign serves topological optimisation based on existing metallic part geometry which has been imported in finite elements code for material distribution analysis. The load case corresponding to the car seat pull test ECE-R14 standard has been applied. Optimisation results indicated that composite part could reach 35 % of the initial steel part. However special treatment should be given to areas under front and rear load bearing points in order to prevent them from the local stress concentration. Therefore final seat plate design has reinforcement areas (patches) under the frame fixation points.

For validation purposes prototypes have been examined by non-destructive methods comparing experimental and numerical eigenfrequencies and mode shape results. It was confirmed that experimental prototypes has close matching mode shapes and eigenfrequencies values.

In addition local loading on the seat plate fragment have been performed prior to general installation of the whole structure in the truck cabin and executing seat pull-out test. Test demonstrated that displacements at the required load level do not exceed design load values.

1 INTRODUCTION

Thermoplastic textile composites with glass and polypropylene (GF/PP) hybrid yarns provide relatively high strength/weight compared to steel. Considering that thermoplastic composites requires significantly less time to produce (compared to thermosets) [1,2] they could be further applied to substitute traditional metal stamping processes to assure the high production rate as required for automotive part production.

Taking into the account that limit stress of thermoplastic composite ($\sigma_x \sim 350$ MPa) is close to steel yield strength (for example for S355 steel grade $f_y = 355$ MPa) such material could be successfully utilised for replacing metallic parts for example in truck cabin) [3]. Usually sheet metal is being applied for these needs due to convenient manufacturing process by cold stamping. However taking steps towards introduction of composites requires additional manufacturing steps of hot pressing and complex temperature control during processing. In addition draping aspects should be considered to avoid wrinkles on component edges [4].

Some of these challenges are have been included in European commission 7th Framework project MAPICC 3D [5]. The aim of the project is up-scaling of the 3D thermoplastic composite part manufacturing applying latest advantages in high-performance textile industries. Part of the project named TRUCK-MAPICC is supposed to provide lightweight alternative to cargo truck cabin parts based thermoplastic composites made of weft knitted fabrics [6] and 3D interlock fabric [7].

The main advantages of these fabric types are improved mechanical properties in out of plane direction and possibility to make high thickness prefabs.

Present research is devoted to validation and quality assessment of the previously optimised composite seat plate prototypes by means of modal analysis and bolt pull-out tests on seat plate fragment. Also a brief overview of the optimisation methods employed to obtain necessary composite topology has been provided.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Problem statement and loading conditions

Seat plate in truck cabin performs a role of support structure for the seat frame. Reference steel part is attached to the cabin ground with spot welds and seat frame is attached by bolts. Main loading factors interacting with the current structure is horizontal drag force applied by ECE-R14 standard as shown in Figure 1. According to this standard mass of the driver and seat increases several times during extreme braking or frontal crash. Only N_2 vehicle class is considered.

	N_1 ($m < 3.5t$)	N_2 ($3.5 < m < 12t$)	N_3 ($m > 12t$)
Shoulder Block	13.5kN	6.75kN	4.5 kN
Lap Block	13.5kN	6.75kN	4.5 kN
Seat	20x seat weight	10x seat weight	6.6x seat weight

Figure 1. Applied load vectors and load values depending on the vehicle class.

2.2 Numerical modeling

VISUAL CRASH-PAM (by ESI Group) finite element code has been employed to process the input files of geometry of a structure and to formulate the loads and boundary conditions. CRASH-PAM is considered as convenient tool for solving static and dynamic tasks [8]. The boundary conditions have been applied to perimeter nodes of the lower edge restricting the translations in all

three directions. Applied reaction forces have been extracted from automotive seat pull test according to ECE-R14 standard. In such a way the horizontal pull force (inclined 10 degrees upwards) is transformed into the vertical and the horizontal components acting to seat connection points. In order to decrease this task complexity and to avoid modelling whole seat structure - forces acting on each support point have been extracted from full scale truck model.

In front part of the structure the vertical load vectors are pointed downward while rear part's loads upwards (Figure 2). Depending on the vehicle class two types of loads should be considered. In current study only N₂ class case has been applied.

Figure 2. Structure mesh and load vectors acting on seat plate support points

ANSYS Shell93 [9] element type with six degrees of freedom per node has been assigned for topology optimisation task. Employed element type have orthotropic structure with material properties assigned close to polypropylene/glass fibre laminate [3] of $E_x = 20.7$ GPa, $E_y = 18.2$ GPa, $G_{xy} = 3.3$ GPa and Poisson's ratio of 0.13.

2.3 Optimisation tasks

Topology optimisation results of volume distributions on the seat plate surface is displayed in Figure 3. Blue colour represents areas where material should be taken away and red –where it should be kept.

Figure 3. Volume distribution in structure at various volume restraints.

It may be clearly identified in all plots that less stressed part of the structure is the centre where material should only be kept for non-structural purposes. Largest material volume / thickness should be kept under loading points. Currently there is no common practice of converting topology optimisation results into final product design, therefore manual interacting by engineer is still most reliable method [9]. Acquired knowledge about material distribution served as input data for further development of functional product involving feasibility studies of introducing reinforcement patches in composite pre-form.

Locations of thicker reinforcement areas have been assigned following the main stress directions and information provided from topology plots. Primary load bearing areas have been placed on the vertical zone starting from the skew plane load appliance points down to the structure baseline. In the same way also have been reinforced areas at the rear of the part. Moreover third thickness property has been assigned to the load appliance points to avoid local stress concentration. Optimal thicknesses for

reinforcement areas were found by parametrical optimisation. For this purpose sequential space filling design based on Latin Hypercube with Means Square error criterion has been employed. Lower bound for thickness variable has been assumed as 3mm and upper as 7mm. Acquired responses have been approximated with ABFC [10] method in VariReg [11] software. Volume approximation function has been minimized to found the smallest value with respect to maximal stresses in GF/PP composite [12]. The results of parametric optimisation are shown in Table 1. Although composite part have larger thicknesses it still maintain less than half of the weight of initial steel structure.

Figure 4. Thickness variables of reinforcement areas

3 PROTOTYPING OF THE COMPOSITE PARTS

Commercially available glass fibre/polypropylene fabric - Twintex was used as initial - assessment material for purpose of rapid prototyping. Both woven and twill fabric types were exploited for test application. In order to have initial verification of prototyping technology a simple assumption - composite part with constant base thickness of 3mm has been produced. Additional steel inserts have been implemented at the fixation points of the seat frame to reduce the stress concentrations in these points and avoid stacking of the large number of fabric layers. The final stack of cut pieces of fabric could be seen in **Error! Reference source not found.**

Figure 5. Prototyping steps. a-fabric lay-up; b- vacuum pressure applied on fabric; c – consolidated part

MEMMERT UF750 industrial oven have been used for GF/PP fabric consolidation (**Error! Reference source not found.**). Temperature regime for consolidation of the composite was set as following: pre-heating at temperature of 170⁰ C for 40 minutes, curing at 180⁰ C for 40 minutes. During the next half an hour structure is cooled down in the oven to the 100⁰ C. After that mold is extracted from oven and cooled in room temperature for several hours before removing final composite part from mould.

4 MODAL ANALYSIS

For validation purposes prototypes have been examined by non-destructive methods measuring structure responses on dynamic influence in various frequencies spectrum. POLYTECH PSV-400 laser vibrometer test equipment was used for this purpose (Figure 6). The PSV-400 vibrometer is a laser based measurement tool for non-contact measurements, visualization and analysis of structural vibrations. In modal test an entire surfaces can be scanned and probed automatically by applying flexible and interactive measurement grids. Moreover measurements can be made over a wide frequency bandwidth. Excitation of the structure has been introduced by software controllable shaker or loudspeaker, depending on the structure stiffness. Structural responses has been captured by a laser vibrometer and converted to graphical mode shapes for visual matching with FEM eigen mode results.

Figure 6. Test set-up for modal analysis on POLYTECH PSV-400 equipment

Two series of prototypes has been examined – seat plates with and without steel inserts. Eigenfrequencies of the parts without steel inserts are summarized in Table 2 and mode shapes shown in Figure 7. For these series of 3 specimens small scatter of the frequencies between specimens could be observed. In average experimental results demonstrates close match with numerically acquired values in CRASH-NVH (ESI Group) [8] finite element code.

Eigenfreq. No.	Set 1		Set 2		Set 3		FEM
	Hz	$\Delta, \%$	Hz	$\Delta, \%$	Hz	$\Delta, \%$	
1	43.75	3.59	42	7.45	43	5.24	45.38
2	133	-30.1	118.25	-15.69	113	-10.56	102.21
3	216.7	-7.66	196.75	2.25	219	-8.8	201.28
4	238.5	-6.6	216.7	3.15			223.74
5			260	-6.67	262.5	-7.7	243.74
6	290.25	4	288.5	4.58	301	0.44	302.34
7	420.25	-1.97	415	-0.7	401.75	2.52	412.13
8	473.75	-1.88			469	-0.86	465.01

Table 2: Experimental and numerical eigenfrequency values.

Figure 7: Experimental and numerical eigenfrequency values for specimens without steel inserts (Upper row – numerical eigenfrequencies; lower – experimentally acquired)

Eigenfrequencies of the parts without steel inserts are summarized in Table 3 and mode shapes shown in Figure 8. Blank spaces in the table are caused by difficulties to find eigenfrequency corresponding to the finite element model. Similarly as for previous series a scatter between specimens are relatively small, but the largest difference between numerical and finite element model is observed for 2nd eigenfrequency.

Eigenfreq. No.	Set 4		Set 5		Set 6		FEM
	Hz	$\Delta, \%$	Hz	$\Delta, \%$	Hz	$\Delta, \%$	
1	46	3.1	41.8	12.1	42.3	11	47.5
2	130.5	-21.9	125.5	-17.2	131	-22.3	107.1
3	222.8	-9.1	217.8	-6.7	212.8	-4.2	204.1
4			253.5	-13.2			223.9
5			279.5	-12.7	287	-15.7	248
6	314	-5	311.3	-4.1	318.8	-6.6	299
7							394.8
8	420.5	-4.5	406.8	-1.1	400	0.6	402.4
9	436		435.3	0.9	433.3	1.4	439.4

Table 3: Experimental and numerical eigenfrequency values for specimens with steel inserts

Figure 8: Experimental and numerical eigenfrequency values for specimens with steel inserts (Upper row – numerical eigenfrequencies; lower – experimentally acquired)

In addition to Twintex plates composite prototypes made of weft-knitted and 3D interlock fabric (Figure 9) have been examined by the means of modal analysis. Eigenfrequencies results summarized in Table 4. Large scatter of the experimental results are mainly caused by defects in consolidation quality as well as some geometrical imperfections. It is necessary to improve prototyping technology to stabilize quality of the parts and acquire more results for statistical analysis.

Figure 9: Seat plate prototype made of 3D interlock fabric (a) and weft-knitted fabric (b)

Eigenfrequency number	Value, Hz		
	FEM	3D interlock fabric	Weft-knitted fabric
1	47.5	33.7	43.5
2	107.1	91.5	136.2
3	204.1	182.1	
4	223.9	237	291.5
5	394.8		
6	402.4	359.5	431.9

Table 4: Experimental eigenfrequency values for specimens made of special fabric types

5 LOCAL BOLT PULL-OUT TEST ON SEAT PLATE FRAGMENT

Series of bolt pull-out tests have been performed on small-scale seat plate fragment to evaluate effect of the local stresses through composite the thickness near the rear support point, marked in Figure 10. It is especially important to experimentally validate connection between frame and composite, because interphase stresses between steel insert and GF/PP plate are not fully integrated inside shell model. Geometry of the pull-out test specimens has been created by mirror copying one-quarter of the outer left corner of the specimen. Based on this geometry inverse aluminium mould has been made with the dimensions of 210x210 mm and depth of 17 mm in the centre. In the middle of the mould are bolt holes, for fixation of the steel insert.

Figure 10. a- Location of the support on the stress map. b – Aluminium mould

For initial trials five thermoplastic composite specimens are made of commercially available glass fibre/polypropylene fabric with trademark of Twintex[®]. Thicknesses correspond to those of the seat plate prototype. Addition aluminium picture frame has been put on top of the fabric during consolidation to make smooth outer perimeter surface.

Tailored pull out test-set up was made to perform loading of the part fragment with vertical and horizontal load components as shown in Figure 11. By changing the inclination of support platform it is possible to reproduce both force components on uniaxial test machine INSTRON 8802. Specimen is fixed in support frame by 12 x M8 bolts. Load is transmitted to the composite plate by 2 x M8 bolts connecting U-profile (representative of the seat rails) with steel inserts. Specimen has been loaded up to the load magnitude of the 25 kN.

Figure 11. Test set-up and the view from the rear side of the specimen.

During the vertical pull-out test bolts are stressed unsymmetrically and largest tensile stress act on the rear bolt due to slope of the test rig (Figure 12). In the result permanent plastic deformations occurs in the steel plate, however composite load bearing capacity is sufficient up to the design limit load of 23.2 kN.

Figure 12: Deformations in composite part and view from rear side.

6 CONCLUSIONS

Originally results of topology optimisation indicated that additional reinforcement should be done to the load introduction points where significant local stresses occurs. In the next step employing parametrical FEM model it was estimated that glass/PP thermoplastic laminate material has a potential of ensuring required strength properties at the same time keeping the thickness thus weight reasonably low. Although thicknesses of the fibre composite shell exceed thickness of initial steel part, low density of GF/PP material allows to reduce the weight up to 75 % compared to the reference steel part. In non-destructive evaluation experimentally acquired self-frequency mode shapes were compared with those acquired numerically by assurance indicator demonstrating sufficient predicting stiffness capacity of the prototype. Furthermore a local, bolt pull-out test confirmed that current reinforcement pattern is sufficient to exceed design load value applicable for the designed load case.

Further work will be done to improve the prototype surface roughness in order to attach the composite part with the steel cabin component. Therefore prototyped specimens will undergo the pull out test according to ECE-R14 standard.

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